

NATIONAL PHYSICAL LABORATORY

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Certificate of Calibration

THERMOMETER
19205E

This certificate is issued in accordance with the laboratory accreditation requirements of the United Kingdom Accreditation Service. It provides traceability of measurement to the SI system of units and/or to units of measurement realised at the National Physical Laboratory or other recognised national metrology institutes. This certificate may not be reproduced other than in full, except with the prior written approval of the issuing laboratory.

FOR: FAAM Airborne Laboratory
Building 146
Central Avenue
Cranfield
Bedfordshire
MK43 0AL

For the attention of Jack Farr

DESCRIPTION: Thermistor constructed by FAAM using a Rosemount Engineering housing

IDENTIFICATION: Type: E102AL, Serial No. 19205E

PREVIOUS CERTIFICATE: 2019100006-2 dated 4 December 2019

DATES OF CALIBRATION: 30 January 2023 to 8 February 2023

Reference: 2022110420

Date of issue: 15 February 2023

Checked by:

K Douglas

Signed:

Name: Mr P A Carroll

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(Authorised Signatory)

on behalf of NPLML

This certificate is consistent with the capabilities that are included in Appendix C of the MRA drawn up by the CIPM. Under the MRA, all participating institutes recognise the validity of each other's calibration and measurement certificates for the quantities, ranges and measurement uncertainties specified in Appendix C (for details see <http://www.bipm.org>).

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MEASUREMENTS

The thermometer was calibrated in a test chamber, in air, by comparison against reference platinum resistance thermometers (PRTs). The test thermometer was fully immersed inside the test chamber. Traceability of measurement was provided by calibration of these thermometers to the International Temperature Scale of 1990 (ITS-90) through NPL Temperature Standards.

As requested, the thermistor was measured as follows: thermistor 19205E was connected to a resistor of measured value 100.0 k Ω at 23 °C, and an excitation voltage of nominally 5 volts was applied across the two components in series. The resulting signal voltage across the thermistor was measured at a range of temperatures. The entire calibration was then repeated with a second value of excitation voltage of nominally $5/\sqrt{2}$ volts, in order to enable the evaluation of self-heating by the customer. The excitation voltage and the signal voltage across the thermistor were measured using an Agilent 34970A data acquisition unit with traceability to National Standards. At each temperature, a time of not less than 2 hours was allowed for temperature to equilibrate. Ten voltage measurements were then taken over a period of approximately twenty minutes.

The results of the calibration are shown in the tables below. The values of the applied temperature and excitation voltage are shown in the first two columns of each table. The measured signal voltages across the thermistor are given in the third column. The expanded uncertainties of the temperature measurements are shown in the final column of the tables. The quoted uncertainties relate to the period of the calibration and are not an indication of the long-term stability of the thermistors.

The ambient conditions in the NPL humidity laboratory were 23 °C $\pm$ 3 °C and less than 80 % relative humidity.

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RESULTS

Table 1 – Excitation Voltage of Nominally 5 V

Applied Condition		Measurements	
Measured Temperature	Excitation Voltage	Signal Voltage	Expanded Uncertainty of the Temperature Measurement
°C	V	V	°C
-60.05 #	5.040	4.499	0.08
-49.95 #	5.043	4.108	0.08
-40.03	5.042	3.562	0.08
-30.01	5.041	2.901	0.08
-20.20	5.040	2.239	0.05
-10.15	5.041	1.639	0.05
+0.01	5.042	1.157	0.05
+10.06	5.048	0.807	0.05
+19.99	5.046	0.562	0.05
+29.96	5.044	0.392	0.05
+40.02	5.044	0.276	0.05
+50.11	5.034	0.195	0.05

NOTE: # Points below -40 °C are outside the range of both NPL's UKAS accreditation and approved Calibration and Measurement Capabilities (CMCs) under the International Committee for Weights and Measures Mutual Recognition Arrangement (CIPM MRA) for air temperature calibration.

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Table 2 – Excitation Voltage of Nominally $5/\sqrt{2}$ V

Applied Condition		Measurements	
Measured Temperature	Excitation Voltage	Signal Voltage	Expanded Uncertainty of the Temperature Measurement
°C	V	V	°C
-60.02 #	3.535	3.157	0.08
-49.98 #	3.535	2.885	0.08
-40.03	3.535	2.506	0.08
-30.04	3.542	2.050	0.08
-20.25	3.542	1.585	0.05
-10.24	3.542	1.161	0.05
+0.07	3.541	0.815	0.05
+10.04	3.538	0.568	0.05
+19.98	3.538	0.395	0.05
+29.95	3.538	0.276	0.05
+40.01	3.538	0.194	0.05
+50.10	3.538	0.137	0.05

NOTE: # Points below -40 °C are outside the range of both NPL's UKAS accreditation and approved Calibration and Measurement Capabilities (CMCs) under the International Committee for Weights and Measures Mutual Recognition Arrangement (CIPM MRA) for air temperature calibration.

UNCERTAINTIES

The standard uncertainty of the applied condition represents a combination of the uncertainties arising from calibration and estimated stability of the reference standards, and from the method of transfer to the instrument under test.

The standard uncertainty of measurement is calculated by combining the uncertainty of the applied condition, the standard deviation of the signal voltage readings and an estimate of the reproducibility of the thermometer during calibration. An uncertainty contribution has been included for rounding to give results an equivalent resolution of 0.01 °C.

The reported expanded uncertainty is based on a standard uncertainty multiplied by a coverage factor $k = 2$, providing a coverage probability of approximately 95 %. The uncertainty evaluation has been carried out in accordance with UKAS requirements.

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